

Evaluating Classification Accuracy, Area Estimation, and Area Deviations of Five Algorithms in Google Earth Engine: Policy Implications

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Abstract: Land use land cover (LULC) classification accuracy is essential in ensuring reliable evidenced-based environmental monitoring and policy making, especially within protected transboundary areas. This study evaluates the performance of five machine learning algorithms and their area estimation differences in the Suam region (40,000 ha) located near Mt. Elgon forest located along the Kenyan Ugandan border. The study utilized the ESA WorldCover and the Dynamic World consensus map to derive 863 training samples using an automated stratified random sampling technique. A medium-composite, cloud-free 2025 Landsat 9 image, SRTM DEM, and MERIT Hydro datasets were used to generate an 82-band feature stack composed of spectral metrics, spectral indices, texture bands, and terrain and hydro features to improve classifier accuracy. The final stack was used to generate LULC maps in Google Earth Engine (GEE) for each classifier using six LULC classes. Accuracy metrics such as overall accuracy (OA), kappa coefficient (K), mean F-1 scores (mF1), quantity disagreement (QD) and allocation disagreement (AD) were calculated for each classifier. Results showed that random forest (RF) had the highest OA (93.4%), K (0.91), and mF1 (0.922), followed by gradient tree boosting (GTB), classification and regression trees (CART), minimum distance (MD) and support vector machines (SVM), thereby achieving a balanced overall area estimation. Contrary to this, SVM experienced a complete model collapse, classifying all pixels as cropland while failing to accurately predict other land cover types. This research highlights the role of classifier choices in creating credible LULC maps for planning and management in heterogeneous tropical landscapes.

Keywords: machine learning; Google Earth Engine; Mt. Elgon Forest; LULC; accuracy assessment.

1 Introduction

Mitigation of global challenges such as forest degradation, biodiversity loss and climate change requires integration of policy with accurate and refined land use data (Dingamo et al. 2023). In line with this goal, researchers have compared different machine learning classifiers, and in most cases, tree-based models outperform classical models. As an example, Kavzoglu and Colkesen (2013) reported that Rotational Forest obtained the highest F1 score (0.923), followed by AdaBoost, MultiBoosting, and Random Forest (RF), Bagging, Maximum Likelihood, and Decision Trees. Rotational Forest was better at predicting deciduous,

coniferous, pasture, soil-rock, and urban classes, while RF was better at identifying pasture.

Regional complexities can affect accuracy, for example, Nery et al. (2019) noted that the performance of classifiers decreased with time as landscape complexity increased. Furthermore, the authors reported that Support Vector Machines (SVM) attained the highest total F1 (0.864) compared to RF (0.856), and Classification and Regression Trees (CART) (0.790). RF accurately determined agriculture, sand dunes, plantation forest and native forest, while SVM obtained higher accuracy in determining water, harvested native forest, and native forest.

Cloud computing platforms such as Google Earth Engine (GEE) provide a centralized data catalog, server-side processing, and integrated APIs and interfaces making them efficient in land use land cover (LULC) analysis and classifier comparison. For instance, GEE classifier performance comparison by Al Saim and Aly (2025) identified weighted ensemble method to have a higher validation accuracy compared to RF, Gradient Tree Boosting (GTB), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and SVM respectively. Their findings also revealed that RF performed exceptionally better at classifying cropland, water, and grassland whereas SVM and minimum distance (MD) performed better with buildings and forest classes.

Input data plays a significant role in classification accuracy. This is supported by Shandu et al. (2026) that indicated spectral bands combined with auxiliary features improves classification accuracy especially for grassland classes. Similarly, Godinho et al. (2016) found the integration of vegetation indices improves LULC classification accuracy and had a high relative importance when differentiating between land-cover and vegetation classes. Building on these comparisons, this paper evaluated classification accuracy, area estimation, and area deviation for five LULC classifiers including RF, GTB, CART, MD, and SVM in GEE. A brief discussion of policy implications based on area deviation was also included.

2 Methodology

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted within a 20 km × 20 km area (approximately 40,000 ha or 400 km²) located on the slopes of Mount Elgon (Figure 1). The area is part of transboundary forest between Kenya and Uganda with the study site specifically located in Suam area. The elevation varies between 1700 m to 3300 m above sea level, which

represents the mountainous nature of the terrain. The area lies close to the equator and is between 1.06°N and 1.16°N latitude and 34.40°E and 34.51°E longitude, thereby experiencing equatorial climate.

Figure 1. Study Area Map.

2.2 Data acquisition and analysis

The study used four main data inputs including Landsat 9 (collection 2 level 2), Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) Digital Elevation Model (DEM), and Multi-Error-Removed Improved-Terrain (MERIT) Hydro dataset extracted from MERIT DEM. A median-composite cloud free 2025 Landsat 9 image was composed in GEE. To improve classifier accuracy, an 82-feature band stack was generated composed of 30 multi-temporal spectral percentiles from Landsat 9, 40 statistical aggregations of spectral indices (e.g. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI)), 6 Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix texture bands derived from the near-infrared band, and 6 terrain and hydro features including elevation, Topographic Wetness Index (TWI), and Height Above Nearest Drainage (HAND).

A total of 863 training samples were automatically generated from the ESA WorldCover (v100, 2020) and the Dynamic World (V1, 2024-2025) consensus map. To address the global product uncertainties, and the temporal discrepancies between consensus map datasets and the 2025 study period, samples were only extracted where both products agree. Sample collection was further refined

using physics-based spectral thresholds for water ($MNDWI > 0.1$ and $HAND < 15$ m) and for bareland ($NDVI < 0.25$). A 70/30 training-validation split was applied on the samples across all the LULC classes including forest (FO), grassland (GR), cropland (CR), bareland (BA), water (WA), and built-up (BU) (Table 1).

Supervised classification algorithms including RF (100 trees), GTB (50 trees, 0.05 shrinkage), CART, MD, and SVM (Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel, gamma 0.5, cost 10) were used to produce the LULC maps from training samples within GEE. The validation dataset was used to evaluate the model performance by computing measures such as overall accuracy (OA), kappa coefficient (K), and the mean F-1 scores (mF1). Additionally, the quantity disagreement (QD) and allocation disagreement (AD) were calculated following the framework established by Pontius and Millones (2011), where the agreement is the OA, while the disagreement represents the model’s error. Area deviations were calculated in comparison to the optimal classifier. Figure 2 shows the methodological workflow. All computational resources are openly available in this GitHub repository (<https://github.com/lewismjomba/Suam-LULC-Stability-Analysis-2025>).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Accuracy comparison

The performance difference between the five classifiers can be determined from the accuracy comparison in Table 2. In comparison, RF was superior in OA (93.4%), AD (3.3%), K (0.91) and mF1 (0.922) compared to the other classifiers. GTB was second in OA (93.0%) with most of its errors stemming from spatial misallocation indicated by the slightly higher AD compared to QD. CART performed best in quantity allocation with a QD of 1.7%, though it struggled with spatial allocation (9.9%, AD). MD was impacted by lower class proportion errors and spatial misclassification leading to a lower mF1 of 0.825. Lastly, SVM failed to identify correct patterns (0.0%, AD) and performed extremely poorly with an (32.5%, OA, 0.163, mF1), indicating a model collapse. This aligns with Maxwell et al. (2018), who indicated that high data dimensionality can significantly reduce SVM accuracy due to algorithm’s high sensitivity to numeric magnitude.

Table 1. LULC classes description and training samples distribution.

LULC class	Description	Total Samples	Training Set	Validation Set
FO	Area covered by dense tree canopy (>2 m)	300	210	90
GR	Natural vegetation including grasslands, shrublands and savanna	100	70	30
CR	Agricultural areas including seasonal crops and shallow fields	300	210	90
BA	Areas with > 10% Vegetation cover including soil, sand, and rocks.	28	20	8
WA	Water bodies, e.g., rivers and lakes	35	24	11
BU	Residential, commercial, and industrial built-up areas	100	70	30
TOTAL		863	604	259

Figure 2. Methodology workflow.

Table 2. Accuracy and Disagreement Metrics across Classifiers.

Classifier	OA	QD	AD	K	mF1
RF	93.4%	3.3%	3.3%	0.91	0.922
GTB	93.0%	2.9%	4.1%	0.905	0.914
CART	88.5%	1.7%	9.9%	0.844	0.865
MD	87.7%	4.1%	8.2%	0.835	0.825
SVM	32.5%	67.5%	0.0%	0	0.163

3.2 Area estimation comparison

Figure 3 shows the differences between classifiers' area estimation for each LULC class. Generally, RF and GTB showed similar area estimations across classes, however in comparison GTB showed slightly higher estimates in FO (+122 ha), CR (+176 ha), and WA (+15 ha) though lower in GR (-211) in BU (-107). On the other hand, RF showed minimal estimation for rare classes such as WA (15 ha) and BA (43 ha). CART showed the highest estimate of WA (560 ha) and BA (105 ha). In comparison to RF, GTB, and CART, MD highly underestimated FO (9,707 ha), while strongly

Figure 3. Land cover area estimation by each Classifiers.

overestimating GR (8,106 ha) and BU (3,461.7 ha). SVM results show a model collapse with the largest overestimation of CR (39,728 ha), while severely underestimating all the other classes.

3.3 Area deviations and its Policy Implications

The differences in classifier accuracy can be reflected in area size calculations (Figure 4). Using RF as the comparison baseline, different area deviations were calculated. Such a comparison highlights how classifier choice can alter landscape partitioning, ultimately

affecting policy relevant land cover statistics. For instance, the -25% underestimation of forest by MD would cause extreme undervaluation of carbon stocks and risk of deforestation, leading to inaccurate conservation measures. The grassland overestimation of +45% would distort the grazing capacity and health of rangelands, which would impact livelihoods of the pastoral communities. Underestimating cropland by -5% would skew the agricultural statistics and food security assessment. Massive water overestimations by CART (+4,000%) and MD (+414%) threaten drought preparedness, while MD's urban overestimation (+118%) would exaggerate settlement statistics, misguiding infrastructure planning and development policies. These arguments support the role of accuracy metrics in indicating classification quality and area estimation deviation as an effective measure of impact on policy related to LULC.

Figure 4. Area estimation deviations relative to RF baseline. Blue (overestimation) and dark brown (underestimation). Values in 'k' denote thousands of ha.

4 Limitations of the study

This study acknowledges several limitations. Firstly, using the consensus map to generate training and validation data, in the absence of ground-truth data, transfers label uncertainties to the model. Secondly, random splitting may introduce spatial autocorrelation where pixels from the same neighbourhood can appear in both training and testing sets, potentially overestimating the model accuracy. To correct this, future studies can use spatial block cross-validation techniques. Thirdly, the hypercube was not scaled, thereby affecting the performance of SVM, therefore, incorporation of feature scaling should be considered for future studies. Lastly, due to the natural scarcity of WA and BA classes in the study area and consequently their small sample sizes, their accuracies can be treated as approximations rather than exact estimates.

5 Conclusion

The study focused on classifier comparison in line with accuracy assessment, area estimation and deviation. Overall, RF was the best performing algorithm, with the highest combination of OA, K, mF1, while balancing quantity and allocation errors. Concurrently, GTB yielded almost similar accuracy and landscape partitioning estimates, indicating robustness and consistency of ensemble tree-based methods in LULC classification. Comparatively, CART had more errors in spatial allocation, especially in rare classes whereas MD classifier had systematic biases resulting in underestimation of forests and overestimation of grassland and urban areas. SVM classifier performed very poorly with majority of the pixels being classified as cropland. The area estimates comparison revealed that even classifiers with relatively high accuracy can incur significant errors in mapping LULC classes. Such errors can mislead landcover statistics and impact policy application on forest conservation, water management, agricultural planning, and urban development assessment.

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